

Publishing Curriculum Vitae using Weblog: An Investigation on its Usefulness, Ease of Use, and Behavioral Intention to Use

Chng Pei Eng., Mah, Boon Yih., Chng Pei Cheng

Abstract—In this cyber age, the job market has been rapidly transforming and being digitalized. Submitting a paper-based curriculum vitae (CV) nowadays does not grant a job seeker a high employability rate. This paper calls for attention on the creation of mobile Curriculum Vitae or m-CV (<http://m-curriculumvitae.blogspot.com>), a sample of an individual CV developed using weblog, which can enhance the job hunter especially fresh graduate's higher marketability rate. This study is designed to identify the perceptions held by Malaysian university students regarding m-CV grounded on a modified Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). It measures the strength and the direction of relationships among three major variables – Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Behavioral Intention (BI) to use. The finding shows that university students generally accepted adopting m-CV since they perceived m-CV to be more useful rather than easy to use. Additionally, this study has confirmed TAM to be a useful theoretical model in helping to understand and explain the behavioral intention to use Web 2.0 application-weblog publishing their CV. The result of the study has underlined another significant positive value of using weblog to create personal CV. Further research of m-CV has been highlighted in this paper.

Keywords—CV, mobile curriculum vitae, Technology Acceptance Model, weblog

I. INTRODUCTION

IN this digital age, plenty of business operations and services have been shifting to Web-based and mobile platform. Online business and e-services are the global current trend and become so popular in this decade. The only reason for this phenomenon is they can be accessed via Internet by using various mobile devices at anytime and anywhere. Hence, the job market is also changing rapidly [1].

Since 1980s, all fresh graduates who applied jobs have been required to submit their CV employers [2]. CV can be simply defined as a document prepared by a job applicant, which consists of an individual's record of education background, qualifications, and previous occupations, which will be sent to employer for a job application [3]. Perhaps, many of the old

rules used in preparing a good CV are not appropriate anymore [1]. According to Thistlethwaite, CV is the story of the applicant life. It also provides narrative explanation why an applicant should be offered the chosen job or certainly call for an interview [4]. Although the traditional CV is still being practiced until today, due to the revolution of ICT such as the Internet and Communication Technology (ICT), the self-marketing strategy is now shifting gears; a new format of CV presentation has been proposed as a supplement of traditional CV, namely digital CV [5] or online CV [6].

II. MOBILE CURRICULUM VITAE (M-CV)

Fortune magazine reported that “23,000 new weblogs are created every day – or about one every three seconds” [7]. With this data, it is not surprising about the immense potential of weblog because it may provide a dynamic force in business field. Giving its flexibility structure, its applications are not limited to publish personal experience for sharing information, but also it has been widely used as a medium for advertisement. Based on these supportive reasons, this paper calls for attention on the use of weblog to create an individual CV that can accessed via various types of mobile devices such as smart phones, tablet PCs and net books.

Mobile Curriculum Vitae or m-CV (<http://m-curriculumvitae.blogspot.com>) is a sample of a personalised web-based CV offering people a more effective and attractive way of CV writing, editing, and presentation. It is developed on Blogger.com that the CV can be displayed in both web and mobile views. m-CV is ultimately useful for the fresh graduates who want to enhance their marketability in today's competitive market. By adopting m-CV, the users can print or view the CV via Internet using various handheld devices. Fig. 1 depicts the screen shot of m-CV in Web view format while Fig. 2 shows the screen shot of m-CV in mobile view format.

Besides, personal computers, laptops or tablet PCs have been replacing type-writers, which are mostly found at home to write, edit, and present individual CV in a more convenient and time-consuming way. Since a well-prepared CV enhances the chances of graduates in getting an interview [2, 8], this highlights the significant touch of IT towards the new generations. Thus, the m-CV can be an alternative since it allows user to publish a CV online that comes with rich multimedia elements. Furthermore, it can be viewed by potential employer or recruiters who are looking for the right candidate [9].

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Mobile Curriculum Vitae

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Mah Boon Yih is a full-time lecturer at Academy of Language Studies, UTM Penang Campus, Malaysia. He holds two degrees: B.A. Ed. (Hons) in ELS and M.A. (Applied Linguistics). He is also a language editor of refereed journals and reviewer of international conference papers. His research papers have been published in both national and international indexed conference proceedings and refereed journals. Mah Boon Yih's Blog (<http://mahboonyih.blogspot.com>) has won him a Gold Medal in the 7th ID 2010 and ITEX Silver Medal in the 21st ITEX 2010. His academic nominations include 'Great Minds of the 21st Century', 'Albert Einstein Award of Excellence for 2011', 'Man of the Year 2011', entry of 'One World Series' and '2000 Outstanding Intellectuals of the 21st Century'. He was selected as the biographies in 'Who's Who in Science and Engineering 2011-2012' and 'Who's Who in Asia 2012'. His fields of interest include weblog, language development theories, critical thinking skills and writing.

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HIGHLIGHTS

In 2011, Mah Boon Yih has received 6 honours or awards: nominee of 'Great Minds of the 21st Century' by American Biographical Institute, Inc. (ABI), USA on 25 March 2011; entry in 'One World Series' under the Education section by International Biographical Centre (IBC), UK on 22 April 2011; biographies in Who's Who in Asia 2012 (2nd Edition) by Marquis Who's Who, USA in May 2011; recipient of 'Albert Einstein Award of Excellence for 2011' by ABI, USA on 20 May 2011; inclusion in '2000 Outstanding Intellectuals of the 21st Century' by IBC, UK on 5 August 2011; and the nominee of 'Man of the Year 2011' by ABI, USA on 12 August 2011.

RESEARCH KEYWORDS

CONFERENCE PROCEEDING by [Electronic Article 5](#) [SPSS](#) [Cross-sectional](#) [Interlanguage](#) [ISD](#) [Technology](#) [JOURNAL ARTICLE](#) [Learning style](#) [Mandarin](#) [Mobile user assessment](#) [Second language acquisition](#) [TAM](#) [Web-based instruction](#) [Weblog](#) [Writing](#)

Developing a mobile curriculum vitae using weblog: a cross-disciplinary survey on university students' perception based on Technology Acceptance Model

Tags: [CV](#), [JOURNAL ARTICLE](#), [mobile](#), [TAM](#), [weblog](#)

A traditional Curriculum Vitae (CV) fails to highlight the candidates' strength, skills and achievement effectively. Thus, graduates are unable to sell and present themselves in an interactive way in order to impress the employer. In the digital age, mobile phones and Wi-Fi are ubiquitous; thus, an online CV, namely 'Mobile Curriculum Vitae' (m-CV) is created and proposed to be the alternative. It uses weblog as the developing platform that comes with both web and mobile versions. It can be accessed using mobile devices such as smart phones wherever and whenever they are. The objective of the study is conducting a survey to investigate the acceptance of m-CV on a group of 200 diploma students in one of the Malaysian universities-Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Penang campus using questionnaires based on Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). After conducting a two-hour seminar on the m-CV, a total of 191 questionnaires were collected. Descriptive analysis was done using SPSS based on 4 point Likert scale. The study found that m-CV was perceived to be more useful rather than ease of use. It reports on how far the diploma students are in favor of using the online method instead of the traditional way to create their CVs. The study attests the process involved in user acceptance of using information and communication technology (ICT) in the making of CV that can be modeled and predicted.

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Fig. 2 Screen shot of mobile Curriculum Vitae or m-CV (<http://m-curriculumvitae.blogspot.com/?m=1>) in mobile view format.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In today's competitive job-seeking environment, there is no other better way for university graduates to show their qualifications and experience to their future employers through the use of CV. Therefore, preparing a well-crafted CV is still vital [10]. Furthermore, employers receive many applications for any open positions at one time. Nevertheless, due to the shortage of open positions, many fresh graduates are facing challenges in landing themselves in their dream jobs. Only those who are able to present themselves in the best light during the application and interview process might have higher chance to be offered a position in a well-established company. A traditional CV fails to highlight the candidates' strength, skills and achievement effectively [9]. Thus, new graduates are unable to sell and present themselves in an interactive way in order to impress the employer. Creating a winning CV is always a difficult process for most new graduates [10], it is our concern how to help the job seeker to prepare a digital web-based CV that highlights qualifications that will make one person standing out from the crowd; hence, it will boost up the marketability rate.

Fig. 1 Screen shot of mobile Curriculum Vitae or m-CV (<http://m-curriculumvitae.blogspot.com>) in Web view format

IV. PURPOSE

The objectives of the research are as follows:

1. To identify whether there is a positive and significant relationship between students' Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) of using m-CV;
2. To identify whether there is a positive and significant relationship between students' Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Behavioral Intention (BI) to use m-CV; and
3. To identify whether there is a positive and significant relationship between students' Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Behavioral Intention (BI) to use m-CV.

V. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The three research questions addressed in the study are as follows:

- RQ1. Is there a positive and significant relationship between students' PEOU and PU of using m-CV?
- RQ2. Is there a positive and significant relationship between students' PU and BI to use m-CV?
- RQ3. Is there a positive and significant relationship between students' PEOU and BI to use m-CV?

VI. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Curriculum Vitae

A research team at Universidade de Aveiro has developed an online CV system, which enables users to have an up-to-date CV available always for use anywhere [6]. It used XML for creating CV data storage system. In the year 2005, Galdino and Gotway [5] proposed the digital CV for radiologists to illustrate their accomplishments in the field of medicine. As compared to printed CV, the digital CV incorporates a full-length of articles, animations, images and video clips. Besides, it also turns up to be a better way to solve misrepresentation issue-the reliability and accuracy of information provided in the CVs of medical students, residents, and fellows. The digital CV can be composed in four formats: (1) a CD-ROM or DVD-ROM that contains separate files of articles (PDF or word processing documents), presentations or video clips as an adjunct to a printed CV; (2) a CV in a word processing document (or PDF) with embedded links to articles, presentations, or video clips; (3) an HTML file (viewed using a browser) displayed locally via a CD-ROM or other media or displayed remotely via the Internet; and (4) an advanced composition using a program such as Macromedia Flash or Director, essentially a movie production of a CV. Each of every one of these formats has its advantages and limitations [5].

B. Weblogs

With the release of Bloggers (www.blogger.com) in August 1999, a free virtual online web space for individuals to do posting on any topics arose. It is noticed that the number of weblogs is increasing rapidly [11]. Besides linear text, other features like images, photos, animations, videos, as well as

adding links to the written contents are also allowed. Blogs are found to be one of the powerful interactive writing tools, which enable the bloggers to frequently update their personal journals. The blogger can choose whether they want to do one-way communication only or offer interaction space for the others to comment. Compared to creating a conventional website, blog has become a choice for many people because:

- a) to publish on blogs is simple because the provided tools are user friendly, and it requires short learning time to master it as to compare to create websites using HTML editors;
- b) bloggers need to focus on posting contents, not much on designing and creating blog page; and
- c) blogs offer various added facilities for the use of bloggers [12].

Therefore, creating a m-CV using weblog as the developing platform is the perfect choice.

C. Technology Acceptance Model

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) introduced by Davis in 1989 has been widely used for modelling users' attitude including student acceptance of new technology system. TAM is used to explain the general determinants of technology acceptance. Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), Perceived Usefulness (PU), and Behavioural Intention (BI) to use are among the three major variables that are capable of explaining user actual system use behaviour [13]. Besides investigating the relationships among the TAM variables, this study also seeks to measure university students' acceptance of m-CV. Therefore, to understand students' acceptance of this innovation, the study adapted TAM model as the conceptual framework as shown in Fig. 3 [17]. It focuses on three main variables: PEOU, PU and BI to use m-CV. The simplified TAM model has been applied in previous studies [14, 15, 16]. These studies applied simplified TAM to explore the university students' acceptance towards the use of weblogs as a journal writing tool in English as a Second Language (ESL) writing classrooms. It was reported that simplified TAM is suitable to be adopted in educational context to predict technology acceptance prior to users having or without any hands-on experience using the technology.

Based on the conceptual framework used in the study, three hypotheses are formulated as follows:

- H1. There is a positive and significant relationship between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) of using m-CV;
- H2. There is a positive and significant relationship between Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Behavioral Intention (BI) to use m-CV; and
- H3. There is a positive and significant relationship between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Behavioral Intention (BI) to use m-CV.

Fig. 3 Conceptual framework pertaining the acceptance of m-CV [17]

VII. METHODOLOGY

m-CV was first introduced to all semester 5 and above diploma students of Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Penang Campus, Malaysia on 19 March 2011 during a 'Career Talk' seminar. The targeted students were going to graduate next year; therefore, this one-day seminar was held to guide them with the job interview and CV writing. Besides, it aimed to help students in planning their career path, develop their self-confidence and motivate their interest for a specific career ambition. During the seminar, two-hour session was allocated to present the new concept of m-CV. It is a showcase of m-CV by the creator without touching on the developmental process of m-CV. In other words, a formal training on creating m-CV is yet to be offered to the students. Questionnaires were distributed to all students before reaching the end of the session.

Data examining respondents' attitudes was collected using self-reported questionnaire. A 23-item questionnaire namely *Mobile Curriculum Vitae* (<http://m-curriculumvitae.blogspot.com>) *Acceptance Questionnaire* adapted from TAM model was designed for the purpose of this study. Fifteen items measured respondents' PU, PEOU, and BI to use m-CV. Four-point Likert scale was used in the questionnaire to measure the strength of an opinion (1=strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3=agree, and 4=strongly agree). The rest of the items are related to the students' demographic information such as gender, age, and academic program. Of the 200 students attended the Career Talk Seminar, 191 completed the optional survey with a response rate of 96%. The general demographics of the participants for gender show that 90 participants were female (47.6%) and 99 participants were male (52.4%), and 2 participants did not indicate their gender in the survey form. The mean age of the sample was 21.5 years old. The distribution of students according to study program was as follows: (a) Diploma in Mechanical Engineering (21%), (b) Diploma in Electrical Engineering (13%), (c) Diploma in Chemical Engineering (8%), (d) Diploma in Civil Engineering (5%), (e) Diploma in Culinary Arts (28%), (f) Diploma in Hotel Management (14%), (g) Diploma in Food Service Management (8%), and (h) Diploma in Tourism Management (3%).

Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) for each item, with the Cronbach alpha coefficients for the three variables under TAM constructs are presented in Table I. Cronbach alpha coefficient (α) is referred as an index of reliability in this study. By taking a closer look at the mean

and the standard deviation values, in all cases the mean lies between 2.8 and 3.15. This indicates that the level of agreement achieves above the middle of the scale spectrum, while the standard deviation in each cases is relatively low, ranging between 0.298 and 0.566. As shown in Table I, PEOU consisted of 5 items and achieved $\alpha = .801$, while PU consisted of 5 items and yielded $\alpha = 0.646$. Besides, BI consisted of 5 items and reached $\alpha = 0.831$. It has been reported that the index of reliabilities less than .60 are considered to be poor; those in the .70 range are acceptable; and those over 0.8 are good in most survey research [18]. Here, it is noticeable that all the three variables under TAM construct appeared to have a sufficient degree of reliability since each computed statistic is above .60 [19].

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF MEASUREMENT SCALES

Constructs	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's alpha
Perceived Usefulness (PU)			
Using m-CV can improve my performance.	3.06	.505	0.801
Using m-CV can help me to write my CV easier.	3.04	.527	
Using m-CV can increase my productivity.	3.08	.434	
Using m-CV can improve the quality of my CV.	3.09	.544	
I find m-CV useful in writing my CV.	3.08	.491	
Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)			
m-CV can be easy for me to use.	3.03	.298	0.646
I find it easy to get m-CV to do what I want in writing my CV.	3.00	.410	
I do not face problems in interacting with m-CV to write my CV.	2.82	.502	
I find m-CV flexible enough to write my CV.	2.98	.470	
It would be easy for me to become skilful at using m-CV to write my CV.	2.96	.474	
Behavioral Intention (BI)			
I will always try to use m-CV to write my CV whenever it has a feature helping me to write my CV.	3.02	.566	0.831
I will always try to use m-CV in writing my CV in as many occasions as possible.	2.95	.495	
I plan to use m-CV to write my CV in the future.	3.12	.500	
I intend to continue using m-CV for writing my CV in the future.	3.10	.508	
I expect the use of m-CV to write my CV to continue in the future.	3.15	.502	

Correlation analysis was used to test the hypotheses. It examined students' perception about m-CV through measuring the strength and the direction of relationships among three variables – PEOU, PU and BI. Their relationships were explained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

VIII. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, m-CV has been proposed as a new way of CV presentation instead of using the traditional CV in paper

format. In order to find out whether this innovation can be in favor among the students who may deploy this technology in future, according to TAM, two user beliefs –PEOU and PU are the primary and secondary determinants that will constitute the users' BI of using this new technology. Therefore, the relationships between PEOU, PU and BI become the core study of this paper. The correlation coefficients between PEOU, PU, and BI in this study are depicted in Table II.

TABLE II
CORRELATION MATRIX FOR PEOU, PU, AND BI

		Perceived Ease of Use	Perceived Usefulness	Behavioral Intention to Use
Perceived Ease of Use	Pearson Correlation	1	.516(**)	.465(**)
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	191	191	191
Perceived Usefulness	Pearson Correlation	.516(**)	1	.713(**)
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	191	191	191
Behavioral Intention to Use	Pearson Correlation	.465(**)	.713(**)	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	191	191	191

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Pearson product moment correlation statistics was used to show the relationship between PEOU and PU. There is a positive correlation between PEOU and PU ($r=0.516$, $p<.01$) at the significant level of one per cent. Since there is a positive and significant relationship that exists between PEOU and PU, the first hypothesis is fail to be rejected - *There is a positive and significant relationship between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Perceived Usefulness (PU) of using m-CV.* Thus, the result indicates that although it is just a showcase of m-CV without hand-on exposure, the subjects had already in mind that m-CV was easy to use which enhanced the PEOU on PU. We can rationalize that using weblog to create m-CV is easy. This can be explained that setting up a weblog needs not any programming knowledge [12].

As shown in Table II, there is a strong positive correlation between PU and BI ($r=0.713$, $p<.01$) at the significant level of one per cent. Based on the existence of the positive and significant relationship between PU and BI, the second hypothesis is fail to be rejected - *There is a positive and significant relationship between Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Behavioral Intention (BI) to use m-CV.* This result suggests that although the respondents did not obtain any hands-on experience on creating m-CV, a real association existed between the two variables – PU and BI. The result denotes that the subjects discovered the usefulness of m-CV, which directly increased their intention to use m-CV.

Lastly, PEOU is moderately associated with BI ($r= 0.465$, $p<.01$) at the significant level of one per cent. Hence, based on

the positive and significant relationship between PEOU and BI, the third hypothesis is fail to be rejected -*There is a positive and significant relationship between Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) and Behavioral Intention (BI) to use m-CV.* Perhaps, with the support of hands-on-training on how to create own m-CV, more respondents will find m-CV is easy to use [16]. However, the moderate association between PEOU and BI suggests that m-CV had been found easy to use that the genuine relationship between PEOU and BI was strengthened.

Fig. 4 helps to conceptualize the relationship between the PEOU, PU, and BI, which emerged from the data analysis process. The result is based on the simplified TAM that shows the underlying factors of the acceptance of m-CV among Malaysian university students.

Fig. 4 Results of hypotheses testing

IX. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study makes an important contribution to user acceptance of m-CV. The findings enable higher education institutions to better way in preparing higher marketability graduates. This can be achieved by implementing the correct module to guide the students towards getting their dream jobs – creating m-CV. The training on how to create personal m-CV can further help to improve the job related soft skills. m-CV is expected to have a great potential to provide many benefits to job seekers. Employers will be impressed with applicants who are able to present themselves in an appealing manner; thus, this will rise to the top of the applicant pool. With the highlight of creativity, innovation, and ICT savvy, the applicant with m-CV will earn extra credit compared to the applicant with paper format CV.

There is ample opportunity to further research in the area of m-CV. This paper primary focused on the acceptance of m-CV among Malaysian university students. A further implication of this study could be investigating the acceptance of m-CV from the employers' perspective. This could provide an extension of the technology acceptance model in terms of the use of m-CV technology. Additionally, a quantitative study could be undertaken for a wider range of population sample. This could determine the implication of m-CV on a wider scale and enforce the validity of the study. Some areas for further research are:

- What are the factors affecting user acceptance of m-CV from employers' point of view?

- How does training and other supportive elements impact on the acceptance of m-CV?
- What are the patterns of user acceptance of m-CV on a global scale in other countries and regions?

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